

(MeOH), showed positive Libermann-Burchard test for steroids; acetate ($\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Et}_3\text{N}$), m.p. 124° ; identical (m.m.p. and co-tlc) with authentic sample.

Physalolactone: Elution of the above column with benzene-ethyl acetate (3:2) and repeated crystallization of the eluate yielded physalolactone, $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{38}\text{O}_8$ (M^+ 538/540), m.p. $227-229^\circ$ (MeOH); monoacetate, m.p. $211-213^\circ$. Its identity with physalolactone was settled by direct comparison of two compounds, in view of their physical (m.m.p.) and physico-chemical (ir, uv and nmr) properties.

4 β -Hydroxywithanolide E: Elution of the above column with benzene-ethyl acetate (2:3), and crystallization of the eluates with ethyl acetate yielded 4 β -hydroxywithanolide E, $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{38}\text{O}_8$ (M^+ 502), m.p. 197° ; monoacetate, $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{40}\text{O}_9$ (M^+ 544). Its identity with 4 β -hydroxywithanolide E was settled by direct comparison of their physical and physico-chemical properties with authentic sample.

β -Sitosterol-D-glucoside: Elution of the column with ethyl acetate yielded β -sitosterol-D-glucoside, m.p. $288-289^\circ$ (MeOH); tetracetate ($\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Et}_3\text{N}$), m.p. $166-167^\circ$. Acid hydrolysis furnished β -sitosterol (m.m.p. and co-tlc) and D-glucose (co-paper chromatography). Identity of both the compounds were established by direct comparison (m.m.p. and co-tlc).

Rutin: The aqueous alcohol left after ethereal extraction, when kept at 4° for 7 days, deposited a yellow coloured amorphous powder which was crystallized from water as yellow needles, m.p. $188-190^\circ$, R_f 0.43 (BuOH-AcOH-H₂O: 4-1-5). Flavonoid nature of the compound was determined by its uv spectrum (λ_{max} 258 and 360 nm) and colour reactions (intense green colour with ferric chloride and positive Shinoda test). Acid hydrolysis of this compound furnished quercetin, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_7$, m.p. 312° (m.m.p. and co-tlc) and glucose and rhamnose (co-paper chromatography). It furnished a decamethyl ether [α] -31° (EtOH) and was identified by direct comparison with an authentic sample of rutin.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Professor Anil B. Ray, Head of the Medicinal Chemistry Department for valuable suggestions during the work.

References

1. 'The Wealth of India, (Raw Material)', C. S. I. R., New Delhi, 1952, Vol. III, p. 37.
2. K. R. KIRTIKAR and B. D. BASU, "Indian Medicinal Plants", Singh and Singh, New Delhi, 1975, Vol. III, p. 1769.
3. I. KIRSON, E. GLOTTER, A. ABRAHAM, P. D. SETHI and S. S. SUBRAMANIAN, *Phytochemistry*, 1976, **15**, 340.
4. T. K. BHATTACHARYA, T. N. C. VEDANTHAM, S. S. SUBRAMANIAN and I. KIRSON, *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1978, **40**, 177.
5. A. B. RAY, M. SAHAI and B. C. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **55**, 1175.

6. F. FROLOW, A. B. RAY, M. SAHAI, E. GLOTTER, I. KIRSON and H. E. GOTTLIEB, *J. Chem. Soc. Perkin I*, 1981, 1029.
7. A. B. RAY, A. ALI, M. SAHAI, P. L. SCHIFF, JR., J. E. KNAPP and D. J. SLATEKIN, *Chemistry Industry*, 1981, 62.
8. H. E. GOTTLIEB, I. KIRSON, E. GLOTTER, A. B. RAY, M. SAHAI and A. ALI, *J. Chem. Soc. Perkin I*, 1980, 2900.
9. M. SAHAI, H. E. GOTTLIEB, A. B. RAY, A. ALI, E. GLOTTER and I. KIRSON, *J. Chem. Res.*, 1982, **5**, 346.
10. M. SAHAI, P. NEOGI, A. B. RAY, Y. OSHIMA and H. HIKINO, *Heterocycles*, 1982, **19**, 37.
11. K. BASEY and J. G. WOOLLEY, *Phytochemistry*, 1974, **13**, 2143.
12. A. B. RAY, M. SAHAI and P. D. SETHI, *Chemistry Industry*, 1976, 454.
13. M. SAHAI and A. B. RAY, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1980, **45**, 3265.
14. A. B. RAY, Y. OSHIMA, H. HIKINO and C. KABUTO, *Heterocycles*, 1982, **19**, 1233.

Biflavones in the Leaves of *Juniperus virginiana*

S. K. ROY, M. A. QASIM, M. KAMIL, N. ILYAS, M. ILYAS
and

WASIUR RAHMAN

Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University,
Aligath-202 031

Manuscript received 12 July 1982, accepted 26 November 1983

IN continuation of our interest in the biflavonyl pigments of Cupressaceae¹⁻⁵ we report the isolation of agathisflavone (Ia), cupressuflavone, amento-flavone, hinokiflavone (II) and isocryptomerin (IIa) from *Juniperus virginiana*. This constitutes the first example of occurrence and isolation of agathisflavone from *Juniperus* plants.

The pharmaceutical preparations of *Juniperus* are used for the treatment of hypertension and also as hypnotic⁶. Besides fungicidal and bacterial properties, *Juniperus virginiana* is reported to possess abortifacient activity⁷. Oils from the leaves and shoots are used in medicine. They have powerful diuretic properties⁸.

Experimental

Dried leaves (2 kg), collected from botanical gardens (Ooty), were extracted exhaustively with petroleum ether, benzene, ethylacetate and finally with acetone. The last two fractions were mixed and concentrated, and column chromatography over silica gel using benzene-ethylacetate in different ratio afforded several fractions. The last three fractions gave positive colour tests for flavonoids. They were mixed, concentrated and subjected to preparative tlc using benzene-pyridine-formic acid (36:9:5)⁹ as developer. This resolved it into three bands as JVI, JVII and JVIII in order of increasing R_f values.

JVI was found, on complete methylation followed by tlc, to be a mixture of four methylethers labelled

as **JVIMI**, **JVIMII**, **JVIMIII** and **JVIMIV**. They were separated by plc and characterized as hexa-O-methyl amentoflavone, hexa-O-methyl cupressuflavone, hexa-O-methyl robustaflavone and hexa-O-methyl agathis flavone (**Ib**), respectively by comparison of their nmr data with those of authentic samples.

II : $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = R_4 = R_5 = H$
IIa : $R_1 = R_3 = R_4 = R_5 = H$; $R_2 = CH_3$

Ia : $R = H$; **Ib** : $R = OH$

The compound (**Ib**), mol. wt. 622 (mass) melted at 162-164°. NMR data of (**Ib**) taken in $CDCl_3$ are δ : 2.12 (d, $J=9$ Hz, H-I-2', I-6'); 2.99 (d, $J=9$ Hz, 2H, H-I-3', I-5'); 2.63 (d, $J=9$ Hz, s, 2H, H-II-2', II-6'); 3.22 (d, $J=9$ Hz s, 2H, -II-3', II-5'); 3.09 (s, 1H, H-I-8); 3.36 (s, 1H, H-II-6); 3.47, 3.49 (s, 1H, H-I-3, H-II-3); 6.26 (s, 3H, OCH_3 -I-4'); 6.22 (s, 3H OCH_3 -II-4); 6.41 (s, 3H, OCH_3 -I-7); 6.12 (s, 3H, OCH_3 -II-7); 6.41 (s, 3H, OCH_3 -I-5); 5.95 (s, 3H, OCH_3 -II-5).

The compound **JVII**, m.p. 345°, gave pentaacetate, m.p. 240° and methylether, m.p. 268-70°. It was characterized as hinokiflavone (**II**) by nmr studies.

JVIII, m.p. 315°, gave a tetraacetate, m.p. 196-98° and a methylether, m.p. 268-70°. The structure was finally established as isocryptomerin (**IIa**) by comparison of the physical data and nmr studies of its acetate with those of authentic sample.

Acknowledgment

The authors are thankful to Government Botanical Gardens, Ooty for the procurement of plant leaves. One of the authors (S.K.R.) thanks U.G.C., New Delhi for financial assistance.

References

1. A. FELTER, R. WARREN, N. HAMERD, M. ILYAS and W. RAHMAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 204.
2. N. HAMERD, M. ILYAS, W. RAHMAN, M. OKIGAWA and N. KAWANO, *Phytochemistry*, 1973, **12**, 1494.
3. M. ILYAS, N. ILYAS and H. WAGNER, *Phytochemistry*, 1977, **16**, 1456.
4. W. FATIMA, H. M. TAUFERQ, W. A. SHAIDA and W. RAHMAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, **17B**, 193.

5. S. H. M. RIZVI, Ph. D. Thesis, Aligarh Muslim University.
6. C. P. NAMBOODRIPAD, G. H. KULKARNI and G. R. KELKAR, *Current Sci.*, 1968, **37**, 550.
7. K. L. HANDA, L. D. KAPOOR and I. C. CHOPRA, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1951, **10B**, 173.
8. W. DALLIMORE and B. JACKSON in "A Handbook of Coniferae", Edward Arnold and Co., London, 1931, p. 231.
9. K. K. CHEXAL, B. K. HANDA and W. RAHMAN, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1970, **48**, 484.

C_{28} -Steroidal Lactones of the Seeds of

Nicandra physaloides

ANJANA BAGCHI, M. SAHAI† and A. B. RAY*

Department of Medicinal Chemistry, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005

Manuscript received 16 August 1983, accepted 26 November 1983

NICANDRA physaloides Gaertn, which is a herb and grows wildy in the hilly regions of India during the rainy season, belongs to the family Solanaceae¹. The plant is well known for its insect repellent property and the aqueous extract of the leaves, from which 17 steroidal compounds have been isolated, has been shown to inhibit feeding of larvae of various insect species².

In continuation of our search for C_{28} -steroidal lactones from the solanaceous plants³ and in view of the absence of any phytochemical report on the seeds of *N. physaloides*, this part of the plant material was taken up for chemical investigation. Chromatographic resolution of the ether soluble fraction of the alcoholic extract of defatted seeds (1.5 kg) of *N. physaloides* resulted in the isolation of four steroidal constituents from C_6H_6 -EtOAc (3 : 1) eluates. The major compound was characterised as withanicandrin⁴ (**I**) from detailed spectral analysis and also by direct comparison with an authentic sample. Out of the three minor compounds one, named as nican-drine B, was proved to be a new withanolide and its structure determination has been communicated elsewhere⁵. The present communication describes the characterisation of the third compound, provisionally designated as NS-3.

NS-3, $C_{28}H_{46}O_7$ (M^+ at m/z 484), m.p. 296-98°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +53.3^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$, c 0.13) showed striking resemblance with its congener, withanicandrin ($C_{28}H_{46}O_6$) in its spectral properties. Further, most of the parameters of ¹H nmr signals of NS-3 were very similar to those of the corresponding hydrogen signals of withanicandrin pointing to structural similarity of these two compounds. While the carbonyl absorption band at 1680 cm^{-1} in the ir spectrum indicated the presence of an enone grouping, its presence in NS-3 as a steroidal Δ^2 -1-one system became amply manifest from its ¹H nmr spectrum which showed two olefinic hydrogen signals at δ 5.86 (1H, *dd*, $J=10, 2.5$ Hz) and 6.60 (1H, *ddd*, $J=10, 5, 2.5$ Hz).

† Present address: Department of Organic Chemistry, The Weizmann Institute of Science, Rehovot-76100, Israel.